

Tracking the NFT Revolution: An ML Model to Predict NFT Prices

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Abstract

Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) are digital assets that are becoming increasingly important in the Web3 world, with a market cap of \$50B [1]. The market for NFTs is volatile and difficult to speculate on, but forecasting their future value is essential for investment and financial security. This paper examines the relationship between NFT valuations and a range of factors, including public market data, NFT metadata, and social trends data. These data sources were chosen to enable comparisons with traditional investment classes and to allow for the quantification of qualitative data such as sentiment and engagement on social media and in search trends. The data was then analyzed using various machine learning models, including linear regression and different types of recurrent neural networks, to identify the most significant factors influencing NFT valuations and to predict future values.

Keywords: NFT, crypto-currencies, machine learning, neural networks, market analysis/appraisal.

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1. Introduction

In this study, we looked at the relationship between the value of non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and different factors from three main categories: public market data, NFT metadata, and social trends data. These data sources were chosen because they allow us to compare NFTs to traditional investment classes and to try to measure qualitative data like sentiment and engagement through social media and search trends.

We used machine learning models, including linear regression and different versions of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) such as LSTMs, GRUs, and multivariate RNNs, to identify the features most closely related to NFT value and to predict future NFT values.

The NFT market is volatile and difficult to speculate on, and predicting the future value of NFTs is important for financial security and investment decisions as

they become a key asset class for investors. However, the NFT market is very diverse, with 1% of assets being traded for more than \$1500 and 75% being traded for less than \$15 [2]. Additionally, just 32,000 wallets hold 80% of the market capitalization of the NFT market, indicating significant inequalities and making it easier for rapid changes to occur in the market [3].

1.1. Prior Literature

There is not a significant amount of research that has been conducted in the field of non-fungible tokens (NFTs) due to the recent emergence of this technology. Additionally, there are currently no established venues for peer-reviewed journals specifically focused on the social aspects of blockchain technology (excluding cryptography). Therefore, the sources we will be using for this research are those that are well-reviewed and come from credible authors or companies, including blogs and posts.

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1.2 Market trends, trade networks, and visual features [2]

The purpose of this paper is to clarify the general structure of the Non-Fungible Token (NFT) market and present a method for analyzing its development. The authors gathered data on 6.1 million trades and 4.7 million NFTs from the Ethereum and WAX blockchains between 2017 and 2021. Through their analysis, the authors discovered the statistical properties of the market, identified a network of interactions among traders, and found clusters of objects based on visual characteristics and collections. In addition, the authors proposed a linear regression model that uses the results of their analysis to predict NFT prices.

The categories of Games, Collectibles, and Art, make up 44%, 38%, and 10% of the top five collections in the NFT market, respectively, in terms of the number of NFTs exchanged. However, the Art category has contributed the largest share of market volume at around 71%. Additionally, the top 10% of traders, based on their number of purchases and sales, are responsible for 85% of all transactions. This group of traders tends to trade NFTs with other traders who specialize in the same collection. The authors used AlexNet, a convolutional neural network, to generate dense vector representations of images and principal component analysis (PCA) to examine the similarity between 1.25 million NFTs. The results showed that the first five principal components account for 38.3% of the total variance and can be used to evaluate the ability of visual features to predict NFT sales.

The authors developed a linear regression model with a least squares loss to predict the price of primary and secondary sales of NFTs, using data from the days leading up to the primary sale. The model includes 11 features, organized into three groups, as described in Table 1.

Table 1. NFT features

Network centrality	Visual features	Sales history
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Degree centrality of seller - PageRank centrality of seller - Degree centrality of buyer - PageRange centrality of buyer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Five PCA components extracted from the AlexNet vector of the NFT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Median price of primary and secondary sales made in the collection of interest. - The prior probability of secondary sale.

The authors found that the median sale price of NFTs in a collection is able to predict more than half of the variance in the price of future primary and secondary sales, with more accurate predictions obtained when using a recent time window for the median past sale price calculation. In addition, measures of the centrality of the buyer and seller in the trader network and visual features of the object linked to the NFT together explain approximately one-fifth of the variance. However, this study has several limitations, including the use of data from NFT marketplaces rather than directly from the Ethereum or WAX blockchains, which excludes independent NFT producers. Other factors that could affect market behavior, such as social media, were not considered in the analysis.

1.3 What Draws Attention to Non-Fungible Tokens? [4]

This research paper explores the use of vector autoregressive models (VARs) to demonstrate that Bitcoin (BTC) and Ether (ETH) are the most influential core cryptocurrencies in predicting future NFT prices.

This research team uses the S&P 500, Google search trends, and cryptocurrency prices as indicators to predict future NFT prices. They found that Google search trend data is related to major cryptocurrency returns and NFT collections. In addition to VARs, this team also applied wavelet coherence techniques to examine the relationship between cryptocurrency returns and NFT levels of attention. The findings of this paper indicate that there is no significant relationship between Ether returns and attention to NFTs, but there is a connection between Bitcoin and the prediction of an NFT.

1.4 Influence of Social Media on NFT Valuation [5]

The primary focus of this paper is to investigate the relationship between user activity on Twitter and NFT prices on the OpenSea platform and to determine whether it is possible to predict NFT values using signals from Twitter and OpenSea. The authors also aim to identify which features have the greatest impact on the prediction.

This paper aims to create one of the first NFT datasets that include both OpenSea and Twitter data in order to answer the research questions. The authors used both a binary and multi-classification model to first predict whether an NFT would be profitable and then

classify profitable NFTs into different price brackets. It was found that adding Twitter data to the feature set increased the accuracy of the model by 6% compared to a model that only used data from NFT platforms like OpenSea. The paper also provides insights into additional training strategies and features that could be used in a predictive model.

1.5 Issues in NFT marketplaces [6]

The authors of this paper acknowledge the various issues surrounding NFT marketplaces and commercial ecosystems. The biggest such issue is that of money laundering: a crime that has historically been linked to the commerce of art, which is made even easier in the case of NFTs due to the anonymity of the buyers and the lack of any need to physically transport the art. The presence of this issue, and the anonymity of any other form of market manipulation, inevitably causes erratic market activity that makes it very difficult for any prediction model to function accurately.

It can also not be ignored that the sudden hype around NFTs is characteristic of other short-lived social media trends. From influencers promoting their own NFT projects to public fascination with blockchain and cryptocurrencies, it is still yet to be seen if this public interest can be sustained or hold any form of consistency, and the development and results of this paper depend on it being so to be fruitful in the long term. It is indeed probable that public opinion will sway against NFTs once people have a more clear understanding of the true nature of the NFT market and its actual relation to the blockchain technology.

2. Data Collection and Processing

2.1 NFT Data

There are currently more NFTs available for purchase on platforms like OpenSea and other NFT marketplaces than there were websites in 2010 [7]. This large volume of NFTs has made it difficult to efficiently search and retrieve information about them due to the variety of data types associated with these digital assets.

While it may seem straightforward to index historical data on the Ethereum blockchain related to digital assets, we found it to be more challenging than using APIs for traditional finance markets (such as Yahoo Finance). Ethereum nodes do not natively store transactions by wallet address, so an indexer is required to do this. However, the available indexers for querying the Ethereum blockchain have high developer friction, are

fragmented, or are too costly for this project.

In order to get the data we were interested in gathering related to NFTs we needed to explore more APIs than we initially intended to in our project proposal. The APIs we explored include:

1. OpenSea NFT API
2. Covalent NFT historical data API
3. Etherscan API
4. Coingecko API
5. Moralis API

We eventually converged to using the Covalent API based on our analysis. Covalent API is a well-respected team that specializes in indexing blockchain data across multiple chains, including Ethereum, Binance, Polygon, Solana, Ronin, and others. Covalent has received backing from some of the top crypto venture capital firms and has gained a strong reputation within the crypto developer community, which made our team feel confident in the quality of data used for this project.

The set of NFT collections that we pulled from include Geisha Tea House; BAYC; Cryptopunks; Doodles; Azuki; Deadfellaz; Gutter Cat Gang; Sup Ducks; Cyber Kongs; Creature World; Cool Cats; World of Women; Alien Frens; Lazy Lions.

2.2 Public Market Data

We used the Yahoo Finance API to obtain public market data for our project. This API is well-known and widely used by developers due to its ease of use and access to financial data. Our project aims to combine NFT-specific data with public market data in order to forecast the future price of NFTs, as mentioned in our project proposal.

By including all the tickers in our analysis, we can combine the data from the public market with the data from our non-fungible tokens (NFTs) in a single data frame for easier analysis. Tickers are abbreviated labels used to uniquely identify the publicly traded shares of a specific stock on a specific stock exchange.

2.3 Google Trends Data

In order to understand the value of a non-fungible token (NFT), it is important to consider the hype or buzz surrounding the NFT's associated project. To quantify this metric, we can use Google Trends data to track the search volume for the name of the collection over time.

Variable	Description
<i>opening_date</i>	Date of which information is being pulled.
<i>average_volume_quote_day</i>	Average price of the NFT as of <i>opening_date</i> .
<i>unique_token_ids_sold_count</i>	The number of NFTs from a given collection sold in one day.
<i>ETH_USD</i>	Closing price of ETH token
<i>BTC_USD</i>	Closing price of Bitcoin.
<i>GC=F</i>	Closing price of gold.
<i>^GSPC</i>	Closing S&P value.
<i>^DJI</i>	Closing Dow Jones value.
<i>^NDX</i>	Closing Nasdaq 100 value.
<i>MSFT</i>	Closing Microsoft stock price.
<i>AAPL</i>	Closing Apple stock price.
<i>NFLX</i>	Closing Netflix stock price.
<i>TSLA</i>	Closing Tesla stock price.
<i>AMZN</i>	Closing Amazon stock price.
<i>FB</i>	Closing Meta stock price.
<i>Relative Search Volume</i>	Relative Google search volume for collection name on a scale from 0-100

X (input data)

<i>Events</i>	-1,0,1 indicating bad news, no news, and good news respectively	
<i>Gas</i>	A measure of network traffic, which indicates the transaction fee of purchase	
<i>average_volume_quote_day[opening_date + 1]</i>	Average price of the NFT as of <i>opening_date + 1</i> (the next day's price).	Y (labels)

The PyTrends API enables us to gather this information and merge it with our dataset. The majority of an NFT's value is often tied to the level of hype surrounding the project.

2.4 Significant Event Data

We need to consider other variables that are difficult to quantify, such as news and announcements related to the collections we are forecasting. For instance, when the Bored Ape Yacht Club makes an announcement about a new spin-off or a scammer targets the collection, it can have a positive or negative effect on the pricing. To quantify this, we plan to include an "Event" feature in our analysis, with positive values representing a positive correlation with price and negative values indicating a negative correlation.

2.5 Aggregated Data Dictionary

With the NFT, public market data, and Google Trends data, we were able to build the following data dictionary that would prepare the data to be fed into a neural network.

2.6 Data Adaptations

The crypto and NFT markets operate continuously, while traditional stock markets are only open during certain hours on weekdays. In order to make the data from these different markets comparable, we decided to only use NFT data and information such as Google Trends data that corresponds to days when the traditional stock market is also open. This ensures that the data is properly aligned and can be used together.

Figure 1. A plot of the time series data fed into the RNN

2.7 Limitations and Roadblocks

We intended to include Twitter activity data about a particular collection in order to assess its popularity. However, while we were able to access the Twitter API, we were unable to obtain access to the necessary endpoint(s) for collecting the volume of data we wanted. Specifically, we needed access to the Twitter/search/all endpoint to query for specific tweet information, which requires special permissions. With access to this endpoint, we planned to gather data about the volume of tweets related to the collection as a way to measure its hype. Since we were unable to obtain this access, we had to use Google Trends data as a substitute. We also hoped to use this access to perform sentiment analysis on the tweets about the collection, but we were unable to find an alternative way to do this.

To investigate this further, we wanted to use the Open-Sea Events API to analyze a collection N (that is not in a set of K successful collections, as determined by market cap) and compute a similarity score based on the NFT owners at each time step in our model. This would allow us to understand the relationship between the wallet owners and the potential success of the NFT collection. This research was inspired by the fact that 80% of the market capitalization of NFTs is held by 10% of the wallets (for Ethereum-based NFTs).

Table 3. RNN hyperparameters

Number of GRU Blocks	Hidden Dimension Size	Learning Rate	Sequence Length
3	16	0.01	5

Figure 2. A plot of the average BAYC price per day. The blue line indicates the true value, while the red indicates our training predictions.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Recurrent Neural Network

To begin with, we tried using a recurrent neural network (RNN) to predict the average price of a BAYC NFT. RNNs are a type of deep learning model that can handle sequential data, which makes them well-suited for predicting time series data. The data that we fed into our model is shown in Figure 1. We built several different kinds of RNNs, such as vanilla RNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs, to try to predict the average price of a BAYC NFT. Eventually, we converged on a final model after testing these various approaches.

Out of the different types of RNNs that were tested, the RNN with GRU cells had the highest validation accuracy. A grid search was performed to identify the optimal hyperparameters, the results of which are summarized in the Table 3.

The RNN was provided with the average price of a BAYC NFT over time as input. Following training and testing, the RNN had an average percent error of 80% on the training set, 168% on the validation set, and 185% on the test set. Figure 2 illustrates the RNN’s training prediction and the actual price of the NFT over time.

Given the volatility of NFT prices, these results were not surprising. However, we were unhappy with this outcome. After thoroughly evaluating the use of RNNs for price prediction, we decided to shift our focus away from predicting the exact price of an NFT and instead focus on identifying the underlying factors that affect NFT prices.

Table 4. The coefficient, VIF, t-statistic, p-value, and confidence interval for each predictor.

Predictor	Coeff	VIF	t	P > t	Confidence Interval
Days since release	958.6	548.9	1.166	0.246	-670.4, 2587.6
Avg. NFT price	0.09	41.8	1.053	0.294	-0.082, 0.267
No. of NFTs sold	987.6	4.9	4.163	0.000	517.6, 1457.5
Gas	11.5	286.0	0.732	0.466	-19.7, 42.8
ETH-USD	-14.2	749.6	-0.541	0.590	-66.0, 37.7
BTC-USD	-0.6	705.0	-0.352	0.726	-4.2, 3.0
Gold	165.8	3309.4	1.335	0.185	-80.3, 411.9
S&P	72.6	531499.6	0.136	0.892	-987.9, 1133.2
Dow Jones	-27.7	140946.3	-0.742	0.459	-101.7, 46.3
NASDAQ	-8.0	142726.0	-0.097	0.923	-130.9, 154.9
MSFT	811.9	8842.1	0.792	0.430	-1218.0, 2841.9
AAPL	-553.0	2677.4	-0.499	0.618	-2746.4, 1640.4
NFLX	-57.5	797.6	-0.336	0.738	-396.4, 281.5
TSLA	30.0	456.9	0.368	0.713	-131.1, 191.2
AMZN	28.9	2311.5	0.598	0.551	-66.8, 124.6
FB	238.9	838.9	0.803	0.424	-350.4, 828.3

3.2 Linear Regression

Inspired by the linear models discussed by Nadini et al. [2] and Kapoor et al. [5], we used a linear regression model to determine which predictors influence the price of an NFT. In our first model, we included 16 different predictors listed in Table 2. We assessed the suitability of these predictors by examining various model diagnostics, including the standard error of the regression coefficients, the corresponding t statistics, and the Variance-Inflation Factors (VIF) associated with predictor multicollinearity. The results for this initial model are shown in Table 4.

As shown in Table 4, several of the predictors exhibited significant multicollinearity, indicating strong correlations between the predictors. This can lead to

an unstable regression surface and artificially inflated variances of the predictors, rendering all diagnostic tests and confidence intervals unreliable. This was anticipated, as certain predictors are highly correlated, such as the NASDAQ, S&P, Dow Jones prices, and individual stocks.

Table 4 also shows that several predictors are not significant at the 0.05 level, which is likely due to multicollinearity. It appears that only a few predictors contributed significantly to the model's quality, indicating that several of the predictors can be removed. The initial model has an adjusted R2 value of 0.7, indicating generally good model quality.

To improve the model's quality and reliability, we added two additional predictors, Events and Relative Vo-

Table 5. The coefficient, VIF, t-statistic, p-value, and confidence interval for the final set of predictors.

Predictor	Coeff	VIF	t	P > t	Confidence Interval
Avg. NFT price	1168.0	6.6	11.8	0.000	972.5, 1363.5
No. NFTs sold	903.3	2.7	4.7	0.000	525.2, 1281.4
Gas	11.0	5.3	1.9	0.056	-0.3, 22.2
Relative Search Volume	407.3	4.3	1.8	0.072	-37.5, 853.4

lume Search, to try to capture the impact of “hype” on the price of the NFT. After adding these predictors and recalculating the VIF factors, we began removing predictors that showed significant multicollinearity. The predictors with high p values were retained and the VIF factors were reevaluated. The final model included four predictors, all with relatively low VIFs that are considered acceptable in data analysis. Of these predictors, two were significant at a 0.05 level, and the other two at a 0.1 level. The price from the previous day and the daily volume were by far the most influential predictors of the NFT price the following day. This final model had an adjusted R2 value of 0.69, indicating that virtually all of the model quality from the initial model was retained, but redundant predictors were removed. The final model and predictor information are shown in Table 5.

To ensure that the model did not overfit and that the results were generalizable to a different dataset, the model was also evaluated on a test set. The test set consisted of 20% of the total data, comprising 265 time series observations between April 2021 and April 2022. On the test set, the model had an adjusted R2 value of 0.65, indicating that only a small amount of model quality was lost and that the final model is highly generalizable.

4. Conclusion

The growing influence of NFTs across various sectors such as art, entertainment, sports, and academia has been observed. In this paper, we presented various methods for appraising NFTs for a particular collection. We demonstrated how to utilize various data sources, including public markets, search trends, and NFT metadata, to inform our models. We believe that we have organized the existing research on NFT appraisals in a logical manner to create a new state-of-the-art NFT

appraisal tool. Now that we have identified the key factors that impact an NFT’s value, these factors can be incorporated into more advanced models like a multivariate RNN to enhance the accuracy of predictions.

This paper was centered on the Bored Ape Yacht Club collection, which restricts the generalizability of our research to other projects. We think that further exploration of the use of Twitter data is necessary, considering its importance in NFT discoverability. Additionally, we believe that there is potential for more research on the use of language models and NFT appraisals that were beyond the scope of this project.

5. Acknowledgments

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